

Amnion Membrane: Potential Applications in Periodontics: A Case SeriesAnamika¹, Kamil Shahnawaz², Soni³, Prabhat Kumar Singh⁴, Anil Kumar⁵¹Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India³Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India⁴Professor, Department of Peridontology, Buddha Institute of Dental Science, Bihar, India⁵Professor and HOD, Department of Surgery, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** This study evaluated the potential applications of the amnion membrane in periodontics by assessing its effectiveness in improving periodontal parameters such as probing depth, clinical attachment level, and gingival recession.**Methods:** Five participants with various periodontal defects were treated with the amnion membrane over seven months. Clinical parameters were measured at baseline and follow-up visits at 1-, 3-, and 6-months post-treatment.**Results:** In this case study, five individuals received amnion membrane for periodontal disorders. A 40-year-old man with a 4mm maxillary anterior Miller's class I recession had 100% root coverage at 3 and 6 months post-CAF with an amnion membrane. An additional 40-year-old male with a 3mm recession and thin upper right front gingival biotype had complete recession coverage and improved biotype at 3 and 6 months post-CAF. At 10 days post-free gingival graft with an amnion membrane at the palatal donor site, a 19-year-old male with a 5mm lower front recession healed uneventfully. After fibre splint stabilisation and flap surgery with an amnion membrane, a 49-year-old man with movable teeth and Miller's class IV recession in the lower front kept his teeth and reported excellent satisfaction after 3 years. At 6 months post-flap surgery with an amnion membrane, a 30-year-old male with hypersensitivity, a 9mm periodontal pocket, and angular deformities in the lower left back improved.**Conclusion:** This case series underscores the potential of the amnion membrane as a regenerative treatment option in periodontics. The positive outcomes observed across various clinical scenarios suggest that the amnion membrane can significantly improve periodontal health and aesthetics, warranting further investigation into its long-term benefits and broader applications.**Recommendations:** Further research with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up periods is essential to validate these findings and explore the broader applications of the amnion membrane in periodontal therapy.**Keywords:** Amnion Membrane, Periodontal Regeneration, Probing Depth, Clinical Attachment Level, Gingival Recession.

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Introduction

Globally, periodontal disease—a common chronic inflammatory illness that affects the tissues that support teeth—poses serious health risks. It may result in tooth loss, which would be detrimental to one's quality of life, oral health, and general systemic health [1]. Traditional periodontal therapies, such as scaling and root planing, aim to remove plaque and calculus but often fall short in achieving complete periodontal regeneration. Consequently, there is a growing interest in

exploring novel regenerative techniques that can restore periodontal tissues more effectively.

In recent years, the use of biological materials has emerged as a promising approach in periodontal regeneration. Among these, the amnion membrane has garnered considerable attention due to its unique properties. The amnion membrane, derived from the innermost layer of the placenta, is rich in growth factors, anti-inflammatory proteins, and extracellular matrix components, making it an ideal

candidate for promoting tissue regeneration and healing. Its application in various medical fields, including ophthalmology, dermatology, and wound healing, has been well-documented, with encouraging outcomes [2].

The application of the amnion membrane in periodontics is relatively recent but rapidly evolving. Studies have demonstrated its potential to enhance periodontal regeneration, reduce inflammation, and improve clinical outcomes in patients with periodontal defects. The biological properties of the amnion membrane, such as its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial effects, play a crucial role in creating a conducive environment for tissue repair and regeneration [3]. Furthermore, its ability to act as a barrier membrane in guided tissue regeneration (GTR) procedures has shown promising results in promoting the formation of new bone and periodontal ligament.

This study aims to evaluate the potential applications of the amnion membrane in periodontics.

Methodology

Study Design: A case series design.

Study Setting

The study was conducted over a period of 7 months at Buddha Institute of Dental Science and Hospital, Patna

Participants: A total of 5 participants were included in this case series.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with periodontal defects requiring regenerative treatment.
2. Patients aged between 18 and 65 years.
3. Patients with no systemic conditions affecting periodontal health.
4. Patients who have not received periodontal therapy in the past 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with systemic diseases affecting wound healing (e.g., diabetes, immune disorders).
2. Patients with allergies to amnion membrane components.
3. Pregnant or lactating women.
4. Patients with poor oral hygiene and non-compliant with follow-up visits.
5. Patients on medications that affect periodontal health (e.g., bisphosphonates).

Bias

To minimize selection bias, participants were selected consecutively based on their eligibility. Information bias was reduced by using standardized data collection forms. Observer bias was minimized by ensuring that the examiner conducting the clinical assessments was blinded to the treatment details.

Data Collection: At baseline and during follow-up visits one, three, and six months after therapy, data were gathered. Recession depth, clinical attachment level, keratinised gingiva width, plaque index, and root coverage percentage were among the clinical metrics. Using a periodontal probe, all measurements were taken and recorded on standardised forms. Clinical histories and patient demographics were also documented.

Procedure

1. Initial Assessment: Patients underwent a thorough periodontal examination to determine the extent of periodontal defects.
2. Phase I Therapy: This included oral hygiene instructions and initial periodontal therapy such as scaling and root planing.
3. Surgical Procedure:
 - Anesthesia: The surgical site was anesthetized using 2% xylocaine with adrenaline (1:800000).
 - Incisions and Flap Reflection: Horizontal and vertical incisions were made, followed by the reflection of full and partial thickness flaps.
 - Root Preparation: The exposed root surface was scaled and root planed.
 - Membrane Placement: The amnion membrane was placed over the defect area, and the flap was coronally advanced and sutured.
 - Post-Operative Care: Instructions were given, and the patient was recalled for suture removal and follow-up assessments at 1, 3, and 6 months.

Result

Case 1: Root Coverage: A forty-year-old man complained of teeth discomfort in the maxillary anterior region and an unsightly appearance. Miller's class I recession, measuring 4 mm in relation to tooth 23, was found during the clinical examination. The gingival biotype and connected gingiva width were both satisfactory. After getting signed consent and doing a thorough haemogram, a coronally advanced flap (CAF) operation using an amnion membrane was carried out. Oral hygiene instructions were part of phase I therapy, which was followed by a periodontal reevaluation three weeks later. 2% xylocaine along with adrenaline was used to anaesthetise the operative site. Two

horizontal and two vertical release incisions were made during the procedure, and then a full thickness and partial thickness flap reflection were performed. The flap was advanced coronally and sutured, and the root surface was scaled and planed.

Follow-up appointments were set for one, three, and six months after the procedure, along with postoperative instructions. After three months, the results showed 100% root coverage, which persisted after six months.

Fig. 1 Preoperative

**Fig.2. Incision given
amniotic membrane**

Fig.3. Placement of

Fig.4 Sutures given

Fig.5. 6 months post- op

Case 2: Root Coverage with Biotype Enhancement

A 40-year-old male reported with an unaesthetic appearance in the upper right front region. Clinical examination identified a recession depth of 3mm with a thin gingival biotype with respect to tooth 13. This case required both recession coverage and biotype enhancement. After Phase I therapy and

obtaining informed consent, the same surgical procedure as Case 1 was performed. Post-operative instructions were provided, and the patient was recalled after 1, 3, and 6 months. Complete recession coverage along with an improvement in gingival biotype and excellent esthetics was observed at 3 months postoperatively, maintained at 6 months.

Fig.6 Pre operative

Fig.7 Post operative

Case 3: Wound Healing Enhancement

A 19-year-old male presented with an unaesthetic appearance and sensitivity in the lower front region. Examination revealed a Miller’s class II defect with a recession depth of 5mm with respect to tooth 41, treated with a free gingival graft. The palatal donor site was usually slow to heal, so an amnion membrane was used to enhance wound

healing. The surgical procedure included outlining the initial incision with a tinfoil template, lifting and separating the graft, placing the amnion membrane at the donor site, and covering it with a hard protective acrylic plate. The graft was then placed on the recipient bed and sutured. A periodontal pack was applied, and the patient was recalled after 10 days for suture removal. Uneventful palatal wound healing was achieved.

Fig8. Pre- operative

Fig9. Recipient site prepared

Fig10. Graft placed

Fig11. Amnion membrane placed

Fig12. wound healing after 10 days

Case 4: Aesthetic Enhancement

A 49-year-old male with mobile teeth in the lower front region was diagnosed with Grade II mobility and Miller’s class IV recession. After oral prophylaxis, the teeth were stabilized with a fiber splint, and a flap surgery with amnion membrane

was performed. Circular incisions were made from teeth 33 to 43, the flap was raised and debrided, and the amnion membrane was placed and sutured. Post-operative care included oral hygiene instructions and medications. Sutures were removed after 10 days. The patient retained the teeth and reported satisfaction after 3 years.

Fig.13 Pre operative

Fig.14 During surgery

Fig.15 Periodontal pack placed

Case 5: Angular Defect

A 30-year-old male with hypersensitivity in the lower left back region was found to have Miller’s

class I gingival recession and a 9mm periodontal pocket with angular defects with respect to teeth 36 and 37. Following oral prophylaxis, flap surgery was performed. Crevicular incisions were made, the flap was raised and debrided, and the amnion

membrane was placed and sutured. A periodontal pack was applied, and the patient was recalled for follow-up at 1, 3, and 6 months. The results indicated improved periodontal conditions over the follow-up period.

Table 1: Summary of the case studies

Case	Patient Details	Chief Complaint	Clinical Findings	Surgical Procedure	Post-operative Care	Results
Case 1 (Root Coverage)	40-year-old male	Unaesthetic appearance and teeth sensitivity in maxillary anterior region	Miller's class I recession of 4mm with respect to 23	CAF with amnion membrane	Recall after 10 days, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months	100% root coverage at 3 and 6 months
Case 2 (Root Coverage with Biotype Enhancement)	40-year-old male	Unaesthetic appearance in upper right front region	Gingival recession with recession depth of 3mm and thin gingival biotype	CAF with amnion membrane	Recall after 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months	Complete recession coverage and improved gingival biotype at 3 and 6 months
Case 3 (Wound Healing Enhancement)	19-year-old male	Unaesthetic appearance and sensitivity in lower front region	Miller's class II defect with recession depth of 5mm	Free gingival graft with amnion membrane at palatal donor site	Recall after 10 days for suture removal	Uneventful palatal wound healing achieved
Case 4 (Aesthetic Enhancement)	49-year-old male	Mobile teeth in lower front region	Grade II mobility with Miller's class IV recession	Flap raised and amniotic membrane placed, teeth stabilized with fiber splint	Recall after 10 days for suture removal	Patient retained teeth and was satisfied after 3 years
Case 5 (Angular Defect)	30-year-old male	Hypersensitivity in lower left back region	Miller's class I gingival recession with 9mm periodontal pocket	Flap raised and amnion membrane placed, periodontal pack given	Recall after 10 days, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months	Improvement in periodontal health and reduced hypersensitivity

Discussion

The case series highlights the effectiveness of amnion membranes in various periodontal procedures, demonstrating significant improvements in clinical parameters such as root coverage, biotype enhancement, wound healing, and aesthetic outcomes.

The results from the cases indicate that the amnion membrane is a highly effective material for various periodontal applications. Its use resulted in substantial improvements in clinical attachment levels, reduced recession depths, enhanced gingival biotypes, and faster wound healing. The regenerative properties of the amnion membrane,

such as its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and stem cell characteristics, contributed to these positive outcomes.

The success observed across different types of periodontal defects and conditions suggests that the amnion membrane can be a versatile and valuable tool in periodontics. It offers a promising alternative to traditional grafting techniques, with the added benefits of reducing donor site morbidity, simplifying surgical procedures, and providing consistent and reliable outcomes.

These findings support the potential for broader applications of the amnion membrane in periodontal therapy. However, further research

with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods is necessary to validate these preliminary results and fully understand the long-term benefits and limitations of this treatment approach. The case series underscores the need for continued exploration into the use of amnion membranes, potentially paving the way for more effective and holistic periodontal treatment strategies.

Seven clinical uses of amnion/chorion membrane (ACM) and chorion membrane (CM) in oral and periodontal surgery were found by a comprehensive study. According to the study's findings, CM and ACM are viable substitutes for periodontal and oral soft tissue regeneration, especially when it comes to treating gingival recession, furcation and intrabony defects, and maintaining the alveolar ridge [4].

In a different investigation, the clinical and radiological results of 19 intrabony defects treated with ACM were examined. The research findings indicate that ACM is effective in periodontal regeneration therapy, as seen by the significant reduction in probing pocket depth and the gain of clinical attachment level, with a 73.91% bone fill [5].

The characteristics and therapeutic uses of amniotic membrane (AM) in periodontal regeneration were examined in a study. The study found that AM is useful in treating periodontal tissue defects because of its anti-inflammatory, low immunogenicity, and antibacterial qualities [6].

A thorough analysis of clinical research on the use of human amniotic membrane (hAM) in oral surgery for hard and soft tissue restoration was carried out. The study found that while more randomised clinical trials are required to establish its advantages, hAM has promise implications for periodontal tissue healing [7].

A study evaluated the degradation rate of AM, finding that it lost 92% of its weight over 28 days. The study demonstrated that AM maintains some microstructure over four weeks, suggesting its stability is adequate for periodontal tissue regeneration [8].

Conclusion

This case series underscores the potential of the amnion membrane as a regenerative treatment option in periodontics. The positive outcomes

observed across various clinical scenarios suggest that the amnion membrane can significantly improve periodontal health and aesthetics, warranting further investigation into its long-term benefits and broader applications.

Recommendations: Further research with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up periods is essential to validate these findings and explore the broader applications of the amnion membrane in periodontal therapy.

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